

Classification of bomag compactor designed for small landfill areas

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Annotation: All over the world, compactors are medium- and heavy-duty types of waste compaction and crushing machines. Considered the best of their kind, the heavy-duty high-speed BOMAG soil compactor is proving its efficiency and reliability in large landfills and earthworks. Gaining practical experience from many years of work will benefit the user in terms of their efficiency and economic efficiency. Choose one of the models of high-speed soil compactor three-dimensional waste compactor. The machine is specially designed for its task - based on BOMAG's many years of experience and built to the highest quality standards.

Keywords: Classification, compactor, teeth, landfill.

Fully enclosed front and rear frame and belly pant protection. Optimal compression and continuous traction wheel contact, as well as a durable shell designed for hard vibration.

General view and working equipment of special equipment BOMAG compactor.

BC 462 RB is a waste compactor with a dozer blade.

Fully enclosed frame.

Oscillating joint: +/- 40 ° steering angle, +/- 15 ° frame oscillation.

Special wheel design for optimal compression.

Maximum soil and debris compaction and traction from all types of wheels - kept clean by adjustable scraper system. A modern powerful turbo-diesel engine with a capacity of 195 kW. Equipped with hydraulic overload protection and 4 hydrostatic wheel motors.

High-performance microfilter in the hydraulic system with a ring for trouble-free operation and long service intervals. The wide-opening engine cover allows the best service to the daily service points.

Hydrostatic all-wheel drive: simple and robust.

Bending blade for soil compactor.

The gear compactor wheel is the basic version for low waste.

Compactor wheel with teeth and segments for high compaction.

Soil compactor wheel with cushioned feet and segments.

Easy to transport with narrow design: only 3 meters wide (depending on the model).

This technique is designed to compact solid waste and is faster and more efficient than other techniques in waste disposal. In the process of operation, the protective layers are very well armored, so they serve for a long time.

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